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A SEM/Fuzzy method for the estimation of the SEA coupling loss factors

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Abstract

Finite element models have been used by many authors to provide accurate estimations of coupling loss factors. Although much progress in this area has been achieved, little attention has been paid to the influence of the uncertain parameters in the finite element model used to estimate these factors. It is well known that, in the mid-frequency range, uncertainty is a major issue. In this context, a spectral element method combined with a special implementation of a fuzzy-set based method, which is called the transformation method, is proposed as an alternative to compute coupling loss factors. The proposed technique is applied to a frame-type junction, which can consist of two or more beams connected at arbitrary angles. For comparison, we have also included results using a Monte Carlo analysis for the estimation of the coupling loss factors under the influence of uncertain parameters.

1 Introduction

Statistical Energy Analysis (SEA) has been established as a powerful technique to address dynamic problems in the high frequency range. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) has also been considered as a standard methodology to assess problems in the low-frequency range. Broadly speaking, both techniques work well in their respective frequency ranges. On the other hand, it is also well known that in order to extend the applicability of SEA and FEA methods, i.e., SEA for low and mid-frequency ranges and FEA for mid-high frequencies, some theoretical and numerical restrictions are found.

Basically, for SEA applications, if the main assumptions are filled out, the method works according to the theory [1]. For FEA, however, two main restrictions are well known: the first concerns the number of elements needed to describe the characteristic wavelength of the propagating vibrational waves, which in mid-high frequency range become much smaller than the dimensions of the structure. Therefore, a good model requires a large number of finite elements. The second limitation is due to the influence of the uncertainty of parameters in the dynamic structural responses.

Moreover, and in the same context, FEA has also been successfully applied for the estimation of the SEA coupling loss factors (CLFs) between two subsystems [2]–[5]. The vibrational energy transmission between strongly coupled subsystems based on Energy Flow Methods (EFM) has also been investigated using results of FEA, for example the Energy Influence Coefficients (EIC) and Power Influence Coefficients (PIC) derived from modal analysis [6, 7]. Recently, the so called virtual/experimental SEA based on FEA was also proposed to estimate the CLFs [8]. In this method, the idea adopted to estimate the CLFs is based on the experimental concept of the Power Injection Method (PIM). In order to assess those factors, the energy responses of a number of subsystems are found considering spatially incoherent excitation (*rain-on-the-roof*) applied to a given subsystem. By doing so, the input powers and energies can be estimated by postprocessing the FEA data. The main difference between the EFM and the virtual/experimental SEA is that the former is based on exact expressions for the energies and input powers, instead of estimating them using Frequency Response

Functions (FRFs). In addition, in Ahmida and Arruda [9] a new methodology was proposed for the estimation of the CLFs using the spectral element method (SEM).

Although some progress has been achieved, little attention has been paid, in this context, to the influence of the uncertain parameters in the finite element or the spectral element model used to estimate the CLFs. This paper addresses the assessment of the CLFs taking into account the influence of the uncertainty of parameters and its effect. For this sake, the SEM is combined with a special implementation of the extension principle of fuzzy set [10] in order to form what we called the SEM/Fuzzy approach. This approach could be considered as the first phase during a design process as it focuses on parameters uncertainty occurrences and their effect on the estimation of the CLFs.

In section 2, a mathematical review of the SEM applied to beams is given. In section 3, the extension principle is reviewed. In section 4, the SEM/Fuzzy method is summarized. Finally, a test problem with an application of the SEM/Fuzzy method for the estimation of SEA CLFs for frame-type coupling is presented.

2 The Spectral element method applied to beams

In this section, the SEM is applied to beams based on the elementary Bernoulli-Euler theory, which implies that the effects of the shear stiffness are neglected by putting $GA\kappa \implies \infty$ and neglecting the rotational inertia, $\rho I \implies 0$. Higher-order theories for beams can be found in the literature [11]. For the beam element described above, the following equation of motion is derived,

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left[EI \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \right] + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} = q(x, t) \equiv q_v - \frac{\partial q_\phi}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

where E is the Young's modulus, A is the area of the cross-section, I is its moment of inertia, ρ is the mass density, $q(x, t)$ is the external force which can be separated in the transverse load $q_v(x, t)$ and distributed torque q_ϕ .

Now, assuming that the beam treated here has constant property along its length, the following homogeneous differential equation is defined,

$$\frac{d^4 \hat{v}}{dx^4} - \beta^4 \hat{v} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Considering Eq.(2), the particular solutions are found based on solutions of the two equations described by

$$\frac{d^2 \hat{v}}{dx^2} + \beta^2 \hat{v} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d^2 \hat{v}}{dx^2} - \beta^2 \hat{v} = 0 \quad (3)$$

with the following wavenumber

$$k_1 = \pm \beta, \quad k_2 = \pm i\beta \quad \text{and} \quad \beta^2 \equiv \sqrt{\frac{\omega^2 \rho A - i\omega \eta A}{EI}} \quad (4)$$

Following that, the complete solution can be found using the spectral representation as

$$v(x, t) = \Sigma [\mathbf{A}e^{-i\beta x} + \mathbf{B}e^{-\beta x} + \mathbf{C}e^{i\beta x} + \mathbf{D}e^{\beta x}] e^{i\omega t} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} are the amplitudes at each frequency.

In order to develop the dynamic stiffness for 2 noded element of length L , displacements \hat{v}_i and node rotation $\hat{\phi}_i$, the following expressions are defined

$$\hat{v}(0) \equiv \hat{v}_1, \quad \hat{\phi}(0) \equiv \hat{\phi}_1, \quad \hat{v}(L) \equiv \hat{v}_2 \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\phi}(L) \equiv \hat{\phi}_2 \quad (6)$$

Using Eq.(6) and Eq.(5), the coefficients **A**, **B**, **C** and **D** can be found. By using Eq.(5), the displacements \hat{v}_i and $\hat{\phi}_i$ at any arbitrary point along the beam can be calculated by

$$\hat{v}(x) = \hat{g}_1(x)\hat{v}_1 + \hat{g}_2(x)\hat{\phi}_1 + \hat{g}_3(x)\hat{v}_2 + \hat{g}_4(x)\hat{\phi}_2 \quad (7)$$

with $\hat{\phi}(x) = \frac{\partial \hat{v}(x)}{\partial x}$. The functions \hat{g}_i are the frequency-dependent shape functions defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{g}_1(x) &= (r_1 \hat{h}_1(x) + r_2 \hat{h}_2(x)) / \Delta \\ \hat{g}_2(x) &= (r_1 \hat{h}_3(x) + r_2 \hat{h}_4(x)) / \Delta \\ \hat{g}_3(x) &= (r_1 \hat{h}_2(x) + r_2 \hat{h}_1(x)) / \Delta \\ \hat{g}_4(x) &= (-r_1 \hat{h}_4(x) - r_2 \hat{h}_3(x)) / \Delta \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The definition of every term in Eq.(8) can be found in [11]. The nodal loads are then written in terms of the displacement degrees of freedom (DOFs) as

$$\hat{V}(x) = -EI \frac{\partial^2 \hat{\phi}}{\partial x^2}, \quad \hat{M}(x) = EI \frac{\partial \hat{\phi}}{\partial x} \quad (9)$$

Applying the boundary conditions to the beam, the dynamic stiffness relation can be written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \hat{V}_1 \\ \hat{M}_1 \\ \hat{V}_2 \\ \hat{M}_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{EI}{L^3} [\hat{k}^B] \begin{Bmatrix} \hat{v}_1 \\ \hat{\phi}_1 \\ \hat{v}_2 \\ \hat{\phi}_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

which can be re-written in a compact form as

$$\{\hat{F}\} = \frac{EI}{L^3} [\hat{k}^B] \{\hat{u}\} \quad (11)$$

where $\frac{EI}{L^3} [\hat{k}^B]$ is defined as the dynamic stiffness matrix of the *two-noded* Bernoulli-Euler beam element. The matrix \hat{k}^B is a $[4 \times 4]$ symmetric and in general is complex. For the *throw-off* elements, waves propagate in only one direction and hence they can be obtained by setting **C** = **D** = 0 in Eq.(5). The *throw-off* elements are used to represent infinite beams, which conduct energy out of the system.

3 Fuzzy sets using the extension principle

Fuzzy set has been proposed in literature as a methodology that can be very helpful to analyze systems with respect to uncertain model parameters. In the context of engineering applications, a fuzzy model adopted to a dynamic problem can also help in determining the range of results or simply intervals of confidence, considering non-uniform materials, manufacturing tolerances and so on.

The fundamental basis of the fuzzy concept has its foundation in the theory of fuzzy logic introduced by Zadeh [10]. One important aspect in this theory is that incomplete information can be described in a non-probabilistic form. Such an idea has become very popular, especially when applied to engineering problems. In contrast to the probabilistic theory, where a more initial information in a design process is available, i.e., probability density function (PDF). On the other hand, considering an initial phase

of a design process, when only few information is available, the concept of possibility theory adopted in the fuzzy set methods is, in general, a more appropriate approach.

In terms of framework, a fuzzy set is also considered as an extension of the classical set theory. In this context, Zadeh's extension principle [10] provides the fundamental basis for fuzzy set methods where he states that real valued functions can be extended to functions of fuzzy numbers. Fuzzy set-based methods, often referred to as possibility theory, emerged from the work of Zadeh [10]. Fuzzy set theory is especially well suited for dealing with forms of uncertainty that are inherently non-statistical in nature. Instead of producing single intervals as outputs, possibility theory based on fuzzy sets permits gradations of possibility.

In the following, we recall the extension principle (also see [12]). From the mathematical point of view, we can define $\tilde{A}_1, \dots, \tilde{A}_d$ as the d fuzzy sets with the membership functions μ_1, \dots, μ_d defined on the universes X_1, \dots, X_d , respectively, and $f : X_1 \times \dots \times X_d \rightarrow Y$ as the objective function that maps the universes $X_1 \times \dots \times X_d$ to the universe Y , i.e. $y = f(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ and $y \in Y$. Thus, the fuzzy image \tilde{B} can be obtained by

$$\tilde{B} = \{(y, \mu_{\tilde{B}}(y)) \mid y = f(x_1, \dots, x_d), (x_1, \dots, x_d) \in X_1 \times \dots \times X_d\},$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(x_1, \dots, x_d) &= \min(\mu_1(x_1), \dots, \mu_d(x_d)), \\ \mu_{\tilde{B}}(y) &= \begin{cases} \sup_{y=f(x_1, \dots, x_d)} (\pi(x_1, \dots, x_d)), & \text{if } \exists y = f(x_1, \dots, x_d) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Considering that the fuzzy sets $\tilde{A}_1, \dots, \tilde{A}_d$ of the extension principle are convex fuzzy sets with compact support and the objective function defined as $f : X_1 \times \dots \times X_d \rightarrow Y$ is continuous, then the following *alternative formulation* is equivalent to Eqs. (12) [13].

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B} &= \{(y, \mu_{\tilde{B}}(y)) \mid y \in Y\}, \text{ with} \\ \mu_{\tilde{B}}(y) &= \begin{cases} \sup\{\alpha \mid y \in B_\alpha\} & \text{if } y \in B_0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \\ B_\alpha &= \left[\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_\alpha} f(\mathbf{x}), \max_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_\alpha} f(\mathbf{x}) \right], \quad 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

In Eq. (13), $\Omega_\alpha = (A_1)_\alpha \times \dots \times (A_d)_\alpha$, $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$, denote the interval boxes formed by the α -cuts $(A_1)_\alpha, \dots, (A_d)_\alpha$.

On one hand, the extension principle is based on the alternative formulation, which can be treated easily by a numerical algorithm than the original formulation of Zadeh, Eq. (12). On the other hand, modern algorithms for fuzzy set are proposed based on point-based methods, such as the transformation method proposed by [14, 15].

3.1 Implementation of the extension principle

In what follows, a brief description of the general transformation method is presented. However, instead of applying the proposed method as presented by Hanss [14, 15], an improvement suggested by

Klimke [16] is introduced, which is called the transformation method without recurring permutations or simply the *gtrmrecur*.

The general transformation method proposed by Hanss [14, 15] can be considered the first implementation of the extension principle that discretizes the convex fuzzy sets into α -cuts, and then discretizes the α -cuts into sets of points. He also proposed the reduced transformation method, which can be considered as an improved version of the classical FWA algorithm by Dong and Wong [17] that ensures convexity of the fuzzy results. Only the lower and upper bounds of the interval at membership level μ_j for the i -th uncertain model parameter are considered. In case of the general transformation method, the mid-point between the lower and upper bounds is also considered.

Nevertheless, due to the discretization scheme, only convex fuzzy sets \tilde{A} with bounded support and a single value \bar{m} with $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(\bar{m}) = 1$ may be used as inputs. In terms of accuracy, the results can be made arbitrarily accurate by letting the number of α -cuts m tend to infinity, but at the cost of a high computational cost.

One important point to mention, in terms of practical applications, is that the number of function evaluations N is responsible for the cost of the general transformation method. Here, instead of applying the original method proposed by [14], the general transformation method that eliminates recurring permutations proposed by Klimke [16] is adopted.

In order to check the number of function evaluation N , the following expressions are used, respectively for the *gtrm*

$$N = \sum_{k=1}^{m+1} k^d \quad (14)$$

and for the *gtrmrecur*, we have

$$N = (m - 1)^d + m^d \quad (15)$$

with m denoting the number of α -cuts and d the number of uncertain parameters.

For instance, as shown in [16], for $d = 2$ and 100 α -cuts, the number of function evaluations of the original form of the general transformation method (*gtrm*) is 17.1 bigger than N for the proposed method avoiding additional functions evaluations for recurring combinations (*gtrmrecur*). For the same example, however, with 10 α -cuts, a factor of 2.1 is found. Therefore, one general conclusion is that, in case of large number of α -cuts compared with the number of uncertain parameters, a better performance is found with the *gtrmrecur*. However, it is also important to add that, in case of less regular distribution of the inner points, its results can be less accurate. In this case, it is suggested to increase the number of α -cuts instead of keeping it constant as in the original method.

In addition, it is important to point out that the recent extended transformation method proposed by Hanss [18] cannot reduce the computational effort to less than $N = m^d$ function evaluations (even if monotonicity is detected). For non-monotonicity, the computational effort is significantly higher, i.e. $N = \sum_{k=1}^m m^d$. In the case of the reduced transformation method, this number for the dimension d is defined by $N = m2^d$. Therefore, the general transformation method considering recurring permutations according to Klimke [16] is chosen to be combined with the SEM.

3.2 Computing the SEA CLFs using the SEM/Fuzzy method

In this section, a *step-by-step* procedure is presented for the implementation of the SEM combined with the general transformation without recurring permutations *gtrmrecur* in the context of the fuzzy set theory. For additional information about the performance of the *gtrmrecur*, see Nunes *et al.* [12],

where the present method is also compared to the reduced method, the sparse grids approach and to the *crude* Monte Carlo analysis.

The objective in this paper is to provide information about the confidence limits of the SEA CLFs estimated by the SEM/Fuzzy method. At first, a brief review of the main equations proposed by Stimpson and Lalor [19] for performing a sensitivity analysis of the CLFs is given. Considering two connected subsystems i and j , the sensitivity of a given CLF with respect to another CLF can lead to the following expression [19]:

$$\Delta\eta_{ij} \cong E_{ij}\eta_{ii}\eta_{jj}, \quad i \neq j \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta\eta_{ij}$ is defined as the variation in the factor η_{ij} . The term E_{ij} is the energy of subsystem i when power is input into subsystem j . Making use of Eq. (16), the CLFs [19] can be computed by

$$\eta_{ij}^{SL} \cong \frac{E_{ij}^n}{E_{ii}^n E_{jj}^n} \quad (17)$$

with the normalized energy terms defined as

$$E_{ij}^n = \frac{\omega E_{ij}}{P_{in}^i} \quad (18)$$

In what follows, Eqs.(17) and (18) are used for the computation of the CLFs using the SEM/Fuzzy approach. As described in [12], this can be done by a three-step procedure:

Step 1: Discretization process. First, the frequency range $[f_0, f_1]$ is divided into $s-1$ *logarithmically* spaced steps or 1/3-octave bands, which is more convenient for SEA application, with the central frequency defined by $f_i, i = 1, \dots, s$. The d uncertain input parameters $\tilde{p}_1, \dots, \tilde{p}_d$ are discretized into N discrete parameter vectors $\mathbf{p}_j, j = 1, \dots, N, \mathbf{p}_j \in \Omega_0$ according to the chosen implementation of the the extension principle, i.e., in this work the transformation method removing the recurring permutations. The number of discrete parameter vectors N is determined by the number of α -cuts m chosen for the fuzzy number discretization.

Step 2: Model evaluation. The $\text{CLF}(f_i, \mathbf{p}_j)$ is computed for all $s \cdot N$ permutations. An efficient implementation may vectorize the calls to the SEM model to treat multiple discrete frequencies, or alternatively, several sets of parameter permutations at once.

Step 3: CLF Confidence limits. In this case, the resulting $\text{CLF}(f_i, \mathbf{p}_j)$ are used to compute an approximate envelope. For each α -cut $\in [0, 1]$, where α must match the cuts selected for the discretization with $\text{CLF}_\alpha(f_i) = [\text{CLF}_{\alpha,\min}(f_i), \text{CLF}_{\alpha,\max}(f_i)]$, with

$$\text{CLF}_{\alpha,\min}(f_i) = \min_{\mathbf{p}_j \in \Omega_\alpha} \text{CLF}(f_i, \mathbf{p}_j) \quad \text{and} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{CLF}_{\alpha,\max}(f_i) = \max_{\mathbf{p}_j \in \Omega_\alpha} \text{CLF}(f_i, \mathbf{p}_j). \quad (20)$$

At the end of the process, the fuzzy-valued CLF response at any given frequency f_i can be composed from the α -level sets of $\text{CLF}(f_i)_\alpha$. Furthermore, the CLF envelopes for a given interval of confidence α are easily obtained by plotting the two curves of the minimum and the maximum CLF values $\text{CLF}_{\alpha,\min}(f_i)$ and $\text{CLF}_{\alpha,\max}(f_i)$, respectively, over the frequencies $f_i, i \in [f_0, f_1]$. Therefore, considering that the CLFs are the main SEA parameters, the idea to assess the envelopes is to provide more robust CLFs to build an SEA model. In the next section, the present method is applied to a frame truss-type structure connected at an arbitrary angle.

4 Application to frame-type structures

4.1 Problem definition

In order to show the applicability of the SEM/Fuzzy method proposed above, an estimation of the SEA CLFs for the frame-type junction shown in Figure 1 is presented. Table 1 shows the physical properties for the beams 1 and 2 with mean values and standard deviation for each uncertain input parameter. Different parameterization schemes may be used for the frame junction depending on the physics of the problem at hand. For the proposed example, the Young's modulus \tilde{E} , mass density $\tilde{\rho}$ and moment of inertia in z direction \tilde{I}_z are treated as uncertain parameters. Also, one important to add in this simulation is that, $\tilde{E}_{1,2}$, $\tilde{\rho}_{1,2}$ and $\tilde{I}_{z1,2}$ are not independent, i.e., $\tilde{E}_1 = \tilde{E}_2 = \tilde{E}$, $\tilde{\rho}_1 = \tilde{\rho}_2 = \tilde{\rho}$ and $\tilde{I}_{z1} = \tilde{I}_{z2} = \tilde{I}_z$. For the length of the rods $L_{1,2}$ and the cross-section areas $A_{1,2}$, the mean values are assumed. In this study a simple, and not very realistic, uncertainty model was used only for the sake of illustrating the proposed procedure. The L-beam model shown in Figure 1 (a) consists of two semi-infinite beams, respectively, beam 1 and beam 2 connected at an arbitrary angle θ . In this example an angle of 120° is assumed. However, it is important to stress that it is straightforward to address arbitrary angles and arbitrary number of beams converging to the junction with the SE model described here.

Table 1: Physical properties: beams with uncertain input parameters.

parameter	mean value \bar{m}	standard deviation	dimension
$E_{1,2}$	2.62×10^9	10%	N/m ²
$\rho_{1,2}$	1280	10%	kg/m ³
$A_{1,2}$	1×10^{-4}	0	m ²
$I_{z1,z2}$	8.33×10^{-10}	1%	m ⁴
$L_{1,2}$	100	0	m

Figure 1: SE model for connected beams with arbitrary angle.

The SE model is composed of two 2-noded and two throw-off spectral elements as presented in Figure 1 (a). Using SEA methodology, four subsystems are set-up: two for longitudinal waves and other two for the flexural waves in the x - y plane. To assess the total energy in each subsystem using SEM, a power is input into each subsystem and then the energy is found one at a time. See Figure 1 (b). The CLFs for these subsystems are defined as follows,

- η_{B1B2} : CLF between flexural waves incident at *beam 1* and flexural waves transmitted to *beam 2*.

- η_{B1L2} : CLF between flexural waves incident at *beam 1* and longitudinal waves transmitted to *beam 2*.
- η_{L1B2} : CLF between longitudinal waves incident at *beam 1* and flexural waves transmitted to *beam 2*.
- η_{L1L2} : CLF between longitudinal waves incident at *beam 1* and longitudinal waves transmitted to *beam 2*.

In terms of deterministic response [9] a good agreement of the CLFs was obtained using the SEM with the simplified expressions of Stimpson and Lalor [19] and using the analytical expressions of Cremer [20]. In the next section, the SEA CLFs will be estimated using the proposed SEM/Fuzzy method with the simplified expression defined in Stimpson and Lalor [19] so that a more robust estimation of the SEA CLFs can be expected, instead of just obtaining a deterministic one.

4.2 Estimation of CLFs using the SEM/Fuzzy approach

In this section, the CLFs estimated via the SEM/Fuzzy method are presented. Robust CLFs by means of confidence limits are provided in order to be used in SEA models. A frequency range is set up from 1 Hz up to 5kHz using 1/3-octave bands. In addition, for each frequency band analyzed, the mean square energy values were computed over 10 frequency lines. Figures 2 and 3 show the main results found using the S&L approximation with SEM/Fuzzy approach. The energies for bending and longitudinal waves in beams 1 and 2 were computed from the spectral element solution using the methodology explained in [21]. With an internal loss factor of $\eta = 0.001$ in each beam the energy in the throw-off elements could be neglected due to the length of the two-noded elements, i.e. 100 m. The number of α -cuts used in the Fuzzy method is $m = 7$ and the membership functions are quasi-Gaussian shaped, clipped at plus and minus 3 standard deviations. The results include the *mean*, *maximum* and *minimum* values for the CLFs found for beam 1 and beam 2 plotted versus *Average Modal Overlap*. In order to compute the *Average Modal Overlap*, the following expression defined in [1] is adopted

$$m = \omega\eta n \quad (21)$$

where m is defined as the modal overlap factor, η is the loss factor and n is the total modal density of the L-beam system, which is composed by modal densities for the longitudinal and transversal waves. To assess an *Average Modal Overlap*, a central frequency band is considered. As discussed above, for each frequency band analyzed, the mean values were computed over 10 frequency lines.

Also, a Monte Carlo analysis (MC) was conducted to check the results found using the SEM/Fuzzy method. For the MC analysis considering the same uncertain parameters defined in Table 1, Gaussian normal distributions, but also clipped at 3σ -bounds were adopted. They were generated by the pseudo-random number generator of MATLAB. In addition, to determine the required sample size, the following expression, suggested in [22], was used:

$$N_{mc} = \frac{1 - P}{P - COV_P^2} \quad (22)$$

with P defined as the anticipated probability of failure and COV_P the desired coefficient of variation of probability of failure. The coefficient of variation is defined as the standard deviation divided by the mean. For instance, taking a probability of failure of 0.1 and a coefficient of variation of 0.1, we find, substituting these values, a minimum required N_{mc} of 900. In our case, just for simplicity, we assume a sample size of $N_{mc} = 1000$. Also, its possible to assess the standard deviation in the evaluated probabilities of failure as follows

$$\sigma_P = \sqrt{\frac{P(1-P)}{1000}} \quad (23)$$

In the context of Monte Carlo simulation, P is the estimated probability of failure associated with the sample size of $N_{mc} = 1000$, which is equal to the relative frequency of failure.

Figure 2: Estimation of CLFs using S&L approximation and their envelopes: (a) η_{B1B2} and (b) η_{B1L2} . SEM-nominal (solid), SEM/Fuzzy-*gtrmrecur* (dotted-line) and SEM/MC (dashed +)

Figure 3: Estimation of CLFs using S&L approximation and their envelopes: (a) η_{L1B2} and (b) η_{L1L2} . SEM-nominal (solid), SEM/Fuzzy-*gtrmrecur* (dotted-line) and SEM/MC (dashed +)

Now, with the CLFs obtained above, it is possible to assess the energy levels for the two beams using conventional SEA. Figures 2 and 3 show that the SEM/Fuzzy and SEM/MC yielded quite similar results. Therefore, to assess the energy levels, we have used just the CLFs obtained using the SEM/Fuzzy method. In this example, the energies were computed for a unit power input to the subsystem associated with transverse waves on beam 1. Figures 4 and 5 show the results for the transversal and longitudinal energies for beams 1 and 2. In those plots, it is important to add that the effects of uncertain parameters increase when the central frequency increase, which is clearly

presented in Figures 4(b) and 5(a)(b). On the other hand, in the low frequency range, such influence is less evident than for the mid-high frequencies ranges. Therefore, using such approach, it is possible to take into account the uncertain input parameters and the energy levels can be better estimated.

Figure 4: Energy levels for the beams 1 and 2 using CLFs estimated with SEM/Fuzzy method: (a) Transversal energy in beam 1 and (b) Transversal energy in beam 2. *Max* and *Min* energies (dotted-line) and nominal energy (solid)

Figure 5: Energy levels for the beams 1 and 2 using CLFs estimated with SEM/Fuzzy method: (a) Longitudinal energy in beam 1 and (b) Longitudinal energy in beam 2. *Max* and *Min* energies (dotted-line) and nominal energy (solid)

5 Concluding remarks

The so-called SEM/Fuzzy method, which combines the spectral element with a special implementation of fuzzy sets, is proposed as an alternative approach to compute the SEA coupling loss factors. The spectral element method is used to overcome some of the disadvantages usually observed in finite element analysis. The fuzzy set approach based on the extension principle is used to treat the

influence of uncertainty of input parameters. The idea is to estimate the CLFs and their confidence limits based upon possible variations in the early stages of product development.

A simple numerical example was used to assess the CLFs in a frame-type junction, which consists of two infinite beams connected at an arbitrary angle. The obtained results showed that, taking into account the influence of the uncertain input parameters according to Table 1, the results presented significant variations in comparison with the nominal values. These variations will affect the global results, in this case the subsystem energies predicted by the SEA model.

In this simple example, the variations assumed for the input uncertain parameters are taken as *possible* to occur. When a new project is starting, not much information is available and uncertainty is predicted based upon the experience in former projects. On the one hand, as the development cycle evolves and more experimental data becomes available, a more accurate parameter variation prediction can be made. The pressure to develop new products in shorter time means, in most cases, that there is no time to set up many experiments to provide power density functions (PDF) of model parameters. However, in case input data with PDF are available, more accurate models can be obtained combining both theories, i.e., *possibility* and *probability*. Therefore, for an initial estimation of the influence of uncertain input parameters, the SEM/Fuzzy method proposed here can be helpful to address uncertainty in frame-type structures.

Acknowledgements

The first author would like to thank the financial support provided by CAPES, CNPq, FAPESP, and Daimler Chrysler do Brasil. We are also thankful to Andreas Klimke from University of Stuttgart, Institute of Applied Analysis and Numerical Simulation, for the discussions about the fuzzy arithmetic methodology and for the support given in this research.

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